

EXPLORERS

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University of Massachusetts Amherst

University of Massachusetts
Amherst

College of Information & Computer
Sciences

Laboratory for Advanced System Software

cics.umass.edu

@umasscs

UMass Amherst is the flagship public university in Massachusetts, ranking #24 among public universities nationally. UMass is distinguished by the excellence and breadth of academic, research, and community outreach programs.

The **College of Information and Computer Sciences** (CICS) is internationally recognized for its research activities and has one of the highest ranked and most competitive graduate programs in the nation. CICS also consistently ranks among the 25 computer science graduate programs on CS Rankings.

The Laboratory for Advanced System Software (LASS) investigates systems issues for distributed systems ranging from large server clusters to networks of small sensors. Our past and current research has focused on issues in operating systems, distributed systems, networking, mobile systems, web and multimedia. We are mainly interested in research related to Data centers, smart grids, IoT, and distributed computing. Please feel free to check his publications for details on the kind of work we do.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x2 CHALLENGES

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 825183.

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Health
Energy
Transport
Space
Security

CHALLENGE #17 - UMA-GML-01

→ Green Machine Learning

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

How to build systems that run ML algorithms efficiently

OBJECTIVES

Based on the candidate's experience, we will tailor the program

SKILLS REQUIRED

n/a

CHALLENGE #18 - UMA-MOD-02

→ Modeling of emerging systems

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

How can we build accurate models for emerging computer systems

OBJECTIVES

Collaborate on a paper

SKILLS REQUIRED

Stronger knowledge of modelling techniques

